

Assessment of Knowledge of Secondary School Teachers on National Education Policy 2020

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Abstract: In the current study researchers attempted to assess the knowledge of Secondary School Teachers on National Education Policy 2020. The survey method was used for this study. A total of 200 secondary school teachers in Paschim Bardhaman district of West Bengal were taken as representative samples of the whole population. A simple random sampling procedure was used for the purpose of choosing the sample. A self-made questionnaire was used to know the knowledge of secondary school teachers on National Education Policy 2020. Percentage, Mean, SD were used to analyze the data and t test and ANOVA test were used to verify the hypotheses. It is discovered that knowledge of secondary school teachers on National Education Policy 2020 is average. The study also revealed that there were no appreciable differences in the Knowledge of secondary school teachers on National Education Policy 2020 according to their gender and caste. On the other hand, the study revealed that the knowledge of secondary school teachers on National Education Policy 2020 was differed significantly depending on their location, subject group and teaching experience.

Keywords: Knowledge, Secondary school, Teachers, National Education Policy 2020

Introduction

Education is an effective way to transform the entire nation. Education is a means of acquiring knowledge, skills, values, moral principles, beliefs and personal development. Education is more than just acquiring ideas, it is applying learnt knowledge in practical manners that promote culture, values and personality. Education is essential for the development of the country. In terms of macroeconomic development, it eliminates social inequalities, creates more employment prospects, reinforces societal values, encourages social mobility, innovation in science and technology. As a result, fostering adequate education is an important and necessary component that helps in the development of a nation (Abraham et al., 2022). A quality education relies on a strong and effective education policy. The primary goal of educational policy is to provide equal access to quality education to every citizen of India, irrespective of age, sex, residence, mother tongue or economic status. Education is recognized as a fundamental right of all citizens (Kem, 2020). In India, education policy had not altered in 34 years, most leaders

and stakeholders in education agreed that new reforms were urgently needed. As a revolutionary reform, NEP 2020 proposes radical changes in the field of education. The National Education Policy (NEP) was finalised, reviewed and approved on July 29, 2020. The policy is based on the pillars of “access, equity, quality, affordability and accountability” and aims to transform India into a flourishing knowledge hub (Rajitha, 2023). As the first education policy of the 21st century, India’s National Education Policy (NEP-2020) encounters the obstacle and aim of transforming the country into a developed country by supporting developmental imperatives in accordance with the fourth goal of the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), that attempts to “ensure inclusive and equitable quality education and promote lifelong learning opportunities for all” by 2030 (Aithal & Aithal, 2020a). The goal of the National Education Policy (NEP 2020) is to change the educational system in order to make it more flexible, multidisciplinary and comprehensive. In school education the National Education Policy 2020 focusses on updating the core curriculum, making the Board exams easier, reducing the syllabus to preserve “core essentials” and encouraging “experiential learning and critical thinking” (Devi & Cheluvraju, 2020).

Teachers have the power to shape and expand the boundaries of innovation and knowledge. The primary asset of any educational system is its teachers. They are considered the foundation of the curriculum because they contribute significantly to the transfer of knowledge and skills. Teachers play an important role in helping students develop positive attitudes and core values, as well as influencing their future and behaviour. In the school community, the teacher is in constant contact with students as part of a social network. It is widely recognized that teachers’ work is important and has a profound impact on the quality of education (Patil, 2022). Teachers are main stakeholder of education. The implementation of education policy at the grassroots level is carried out by teachers. Therefore, the success of policy’s implementation depends on teachers. For this teacher’s knowledge of NEP 2020 is very essential for well aware of the latest educational reforms, so that they can effectively implement the policy guidelines in the classroom.

Literature Review

Aithal and Aithal (2020b) highlighted several higher education policies that have been announced and contrasted with the system that is already in place. The benefits of NEP 2020 are examined, along with a number of innovations and anticipated effects on the Indian higher education system. subsequently, some recommendations are made to ensure that it is implemented effectively in order to accomplish its goals. Smitha (2020) attempted to examine the National Educational Education Policy 2020 in light of the changes in paradigms, opportunities and difficulties facing the teacher education field. Gandhi (2021) emphasized the importance of understanding the NEP-2020 imperative approach to Preschooler’s development and its

relevance to disadvantaged populations and community illiterates. Pradhan (2021) focused on several announced policies within the higher education sector and compare with the NEP 2020. Advantages of NEP 2020 along with numerous improvements and proposed impacts on the Indian higher education sector have also been considered in this analysis. Additionally, some recommendations are made regarding how to effectively execute it in order to accomplish its goals. Aggarwal (2022) focused on a number of teaching and learning strategies for young learners that enhance their ability to mathematical thinking in relation to goals of NEP 2020. Gandhi (2022) highlighted how the New Education Policy (NEP) 2020 contributes to the expansion of adult education and lifelong learning programs in today's digital age. With the advent of Atmanirbhar Bharat and Digital India, it is imperative that every member of the community understands the basic skills required to be self-reliant and make valuable contributions to society. Patil (2022) explored examined the quality of teaching, the quality of resources in the classroom and some characteristics of a successful teacher. It also focused on some teachers' professional and personal skills to link them to the UN Sustainable Development Goals and 21st century skills. Vishwakarma and Singh (2023) intended to look at the effects of NEP 2020's digitalisation on society and quality of life. The results showed that the digitization of NEP 2020 has a significant and positive impact on people's lives. Sharma and Pathak (2024) studied the impact of NEP on skill development. It discussed how the NEP process would address India's evolving skill needs. Archunan (2024) tried to explore the impact of India's New Education Policy on higher education. The article also discussed the new education policy's advantages and disadvantages, as well as how it differs from the old educational system. Pandey and Dey (2025) explored how NEP 2020 seeks to bridge tradition and innovation by integrating Indigenous Knowledge Systems into modern education. It highlighted knowledge areas such as Ayurveda, mathematics, philosophy, arts, and environmental ethics. The study also discussed the historical background of Indigenous Knowledge Systems and their marginalization during the colonial period. It further described the renewed efforts to reclaim this knowledge through curriculum reforms, innovative teaching practices, promotion of Indian languages, research initiatives and teacher training.

After reviewing related studies, the researcher found that most of studies are carried out on opportunities and challenges of Teacher Education as per National Education Policy 2020, changes in paradigms, opportunities and difficulties facing in the teacher education field in the light on NEP 2020, the importance of understanding the NEP 2020 imperative approach to Preschooler's development, how the National Education Policy (NEP) 2020 contributes to the expansion of adult education and lifelong learning programs, the effects of NEP 2020's digitalisation on society and quality of life, compare with the NEP 2020 with several announced policies within the higher education sector. Also, studied on impact of India's New Education

Policy on higher education. Few studies have also been conducted on methods of instruction to develop students mathematical thinking in accordance with NEP 2020's goal, impact of NEP on skill development. There are dearth studies carried out on knowledge on NEP 2020, teacher effectiveness in school education as envisaged in National Education Policy 2020, awareness of school teachers on NEP 2020, the role of secondary school teacher for implementation of NEP 2020. The topic is timely and necessarily which means The National Education Policy 2020 is an innovative policy that transforms most of the education systems for quality education and equitable student achievement which comes under recent debates and high time to focus on teacher engagement to achieve the policy's goals. Therefore, the researchers feel that there is a need to explore the knowledge of teachers on National Education Policy 2020.

Need and Significance of the Study

The study on the assessment of the knowledge of the National Education Policy (NEP) 2020 among the secondary school teachers is very crucial to ensure effective implementation of the policy. The teachers are in the central role of elucidation provisions of the policy into practices in the classrooms. Teachers' understanding of the NEP is fundamental to achieving goals such as promoting holistic development, competency-based learning and integration of 21st-century skills. These findings of gaps in teachers' knowledge shall act as information for the targeted professional development and training programs. The study will measure the knowledge of teachers of NEP 2020 which will help achieve better policy implementation and consequently improve curriculum design consonant with the NEP principles.

Objectives of the Study

- **O₁**: To study the level of knowledge of secondary school teachers on National Education Policy 2020.
- **O₂**: To compare the knowledge of secondary school teachers under different demographics such as gender (Male and Female) and location (Rural and Urban) on National Education Policy 2020.
- **O₃**: To compare the knowledge of secondary school teachers under different demographics such as caste (General, SC, ST & OBC), subject group (Language, Social Science and Science) and teaching experience on National Education Policy 2020.

Hypotheses of the Study

- **H₀₁**: There is low level of knowledge of secondary school teachers on National Education Policy 2020.
- **H₀₂**: There is no significant difference in the knowledge of secondary school teachers under different demographics such as gender (Male and Female) and location (Rural and Urban) on National Education Policy 2020.

- **H₀₃**: There is no significant difference in the knowledge of secondary school teachers under different demographics such as caste (General, SC, ST & OBC), subject group (Language, Social Science and Science) and teaching experience on National Education Policy 2020.

Methodology

The present study was based on survey method, particularly, the normative survey research method. It is the most popular and scientific research technique, which consist of analysing the phenomena into their components.

Population

All the secondary school teachers of Paschim Bardhaman District of West Bengal were comprised as the population of the whole study.

The Sample and Sampling Procedure

A total of 200 secondary school teachers of Paschim Bardhaman District of West Bengal were taken as representative samples of the population as a whole. Simple random sampling technique was followed for selecting the sample.

The Tool Used

A questionnaire was constructed and standardized by the researchers and used to know the knowledge of secondary school teachers on National Education Policy 2020. For this purpose, the investigator has studied so many books, journal articles specially related to NEP 2020. This tool comprises 36 multiple-choice questions (MCQs) that cover various aspects of the NEP 2020. Each MCQ includes a question stem followed by four response options: A, B, C and D. One option is correct and the other three serve as distractors. Teacher whose responds are correct marked by 'One' (1), and wrong answers are marked by 'Zero' (0). The questions were reviewed by experts in education policy to ensure content validity and clarity. Pilot testing was conducted with a small sample of secondary school teachers to refine the questions and eliminate any ambiguities.

Statistical Techniques

Percentage, mean, SD, t-test and ANOVA were used to analyze the collected data and the testing of the hypotheses.

Results & Discussion

The results of the study were interpreted on the basis of the results found from the use of about mentioned statistics on data.

Testing of H₀₁

Table 1

Number, Mean and SD of Knowledge of Secondary School Teachers on National Education Policy 2020

Category	N	Mean	SD
Teachers	200	19.88	6.43

Through the help of cut-off point, the researcher verifies the H₀₁. Here Cut-off Point is $M \pm 1\sigma$. It means, Mean = 19.88, N=200 and $\sigma=6.43$ Hence $M + 1\sigma$ is $19.88 + 1 \times 6.43=26.31$. And $M - 1\sigma$ is $19.88 - 1 \times 6.43=13.45$. Most of School Teachers (137 in number) i.e., 68.5% of Teachers were lies between 13.45-26.31 scores. Hence, it can be said that the level of knowledge of secondary school teachers on National Education Policy 2020 is moderate. The reason for the limited knowledge of teachers about the NEP 2020 may be lack of awareness and training opportunities. Due to their heavy workloads, many teachers are unable to make time to study policy in depth. Teachers may focus on immediate classroom concerns rather than long-term policy reforms that limiting their understanding of the NEP.

Table 2

The level of Knowledge of Secondary School Teachers on National Education Policy 2020

Scores	Frequency	Percentage	Level of Knowledge
Above 26.31	37	18.5	High
Between 13.45- 26.31	137	68.5	Moderate / Average
Below 13.45	26	13	Low
Total	200	100%	

Table 3

The t-test for Gender and Locality in relation to Knowledge of Secondary School Teachers on National Education Policy 2020.

Variable	N	Mean	df	t	P	Remarks	
Knowledge	Male	92	19.07	198	-1.650	0.101	Not Significant
	Female	108	20.56				
	Rural	99	22.53	198	6.305	0.000	Significant
	Urban	101	17.28				

Testing of H₀₂

- **Knowledge of Secondary School Teachers on National Education Policy 2020 with respect to their Gender (Male and Female)**

Here the result (Table 3) shows that the value of 't' is -1.650 with the df =198 and p value is 0.101 ($p > 0.05$). Hence, 't' is not significant at 0.05 level. That means there is no significant difference between the Knowledge of male and female secondary school teachers on National Educational Policy, 2020. It is also found that the mean knowledge score of female secondary school teachers is little greater than that of male secondary school teachers. That is to say that the female secondary school teachers are more knowledgeable on National Educational Policy 2020 than the male secondary

school teachers. This could be due to the possible reason that female teachers are more actively engaged in professional development programs and have a stronger sense of responsibility for student welfare and active participation in discussions regarding educational reforms.

- **Knowledge of Secondary School Teachers on National Education Policy 2020 with respect to their Location (Rural & Urban)**

Here the result (Table 3) shows that the value of 't' is 6.305 with the df =198 and p value is 0.000 ($p < 0.05$). Hence, 't' is significant at 0.05 level. That means there is significant difference between the knowledge of rural and urban secondary school teachers on NEP 2020. It is also found that the mean knowledge score of rural secondary school teachers is greater than the urban secondary school teachers on NEP 2020. That is to say that the knowledge of rural secondary school teachers is relatively higher than urban secondary school teachers on NEP 2020. The possible reason for this result may be that rural teachers are more engaged in specific training programs that allow more personalised understanding of the policy. On the other hand, the emphasis of community-based education in rural areas might align more with NEP 2020. While urban teachers might face more administrative challenges that limit their focus on the policy.

Testing of H_{03}

- **Knowledge of Secondary School Teachers on National Education Policy 2020 with respect to their Caste (UR, SC, ST & OBC)**

Table 4

The Mean, N and SD of Knowledge Secondary School Teachers on NEP 2020 with respect to their Caste

Caste	Mean	N	Std. Deviation
UR	20.29	164	6.599
SC	18.12	34	5.347
ST	20.00	1	.
OBC	12.00	1	.
Total	19.88	200	6.433

Table 5
Results of ANOVA for Caste

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	194.815	3	64.938	1.583	.195
Within Groups	8041.060	196	41.026		
Total	8235.875	199			

From the tables (Table 4 & 5), it is found that the computed value of F is 1.583 and p value is .195 ($p > 0.05$). Hence F is not significant at 0.05 level. That is to say that there is no significant difference in the knowledge among the UR, SC, ST and OBC secondary school teachers on NEP 2020. The caste has no significant impact on the knowledge of Secondary School Teachers about NEP 2020. As the mean knowledge score of UR secondary school teachers is greater than their counterparts. It is said that the UR secondary school teachers are more knowledgeable on National Educational Policy 2020 than other castes. The possible reason for this result may be that due to UR secondary school teachers have better access to resources, professional development opportunities and a stronger social network, which gives them more information about the policy.

Knowledge of Secondary School Teachers on National Education Policy 2020 with respect to their Subject group (Language, Social Science & Science)

Table 6
The Mean, N and SD of knowledge of secondary school teachers on National Education Policy 2020 with respect to their Subject group

Subject group	Mean	N	Std. Deviation
Language	19.86	51	6.791
Social Science	21.04	90	6.045
Science	18.10	59	6.392
Total	19.88	200	6.433

Table 7
Results of ANOVA for Subject group

	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	308.624	2	154.312	3.835	.023
Within Groups	7927.251	197	40.240		
Total	8235.875	199			

From the tables (Table 6 & 7), it is found that the computed value of F is 3.835 and p value is .023 ($p < 0.05$). Hence F is significant at 0.05 level. That is to say that there is significant difference in the Knowledge among the Language, Social Science and Science Secondary School Teachers on National Educational Policy 2020. The subject group has significant impact on the knowledge of secondary school teachers on NEP 2020. The mean knowledge score of social science secondary school teachers is higher than that of other subject group of teachers. The possible reason for this result may be that the social science teachers' subject matter aligns well with the NEP 2020, which emphasises critical thinking, social understanding and interdisciplinary learning. In addition, they may access training that focuses on broader NEP 2020 objectives.

Knowledge of Secondary School Teachers on National Education Policy 2020 with respect to their Teaching Experience

Table 8

The Mean, N and SD of knowledge of secondary school teachers with respect to their Teaching Experience

Teaching Experience	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
1-5	47	16.51	4.143
5-10	14	17.14	5.275
10-15	58	19.21	5.869
15-20	55	21.09	6.717
20-25	14	24.57	6.248
25-30	12	28.42	4.757
Total	200	19.88	6.433

Table 9
Results of ANOVA for Teaching Experience

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	1928.008	5	385.602	11.859	.000
Within Groups	6307.867	194	32.515		
Total	8235.875	199			

From the tables (Table 8 & 9), it is found that the computed value of F is 11.859 and p value is .000 ($p < 0.05$). Hence F is significant at 0.05 level. That is to say that there is significant difference in the Knowledge among the teaching experience of Secondary School Teachers on National Educational Policy 2020. The teaching experience has significant impact on the knowledge of Secondary School Teachers on NEP 2020. The mean knowledge score of secondary school teachers with more teaching experience is higher than that of other teachers. The possible reason for this finding could be that experienced teachers have a better understanding of education policy and how it actually operates. With time, they have become skilled at coping with change, having been to professional development workshops and actively engaged in new teaching methods. Their knowledge of the evolving education system provides a deeper understanding of the important concepts of NEP 2020.

Educational Implications

This study has several significant educational implications—

- This study will be very much helpful for improving the quality of education at school level.
- The current study will be great assistance to decision makers, educational planners and administrators to know the current status of secondary school teachers' knowledge on National Education Policy 2020.
- This study will helpful for motivating the teachers.
- This study can help educational planners to discover main difficulties with teachers and develop solutions to make it better for students' education.
- The impact of teacher knowledge on national education policy will further improve the classroom.
- Special efforts should be provided to improve the knowledge of male, urban, novice and graduate pass secondary school teachers on National Education Policy 2020.
- Workshops and awareness programs on NEP 2020 can be organized for teachers to develop a favorable knowledge towards it.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the study on knowledge among secondary school teachers regarding the National Education Policy (NEP) reveals great deals of information about secondary school teachers understanding of the NEP 2020. The findings indicate a moderate level of knowledge of teachers on NEP 2020. Female teachers demonstrated higher knowledge scores than male teachers. However, rural teachers demonstrated higher knowledge scores than their urban counterparts. Additionally, teaching experience emerged as a significant factor influencing knowledge, while educational qualifications and caste did not. Notably, social science teachers exhibited higher knowledge scores compared to their peers from other subject groups. To effectively implement NEP 2020, policymakers and educational administrators must consider these factors and develop targeted training programs to enhance teachers' knowledge and understanding of the policy. These programs will provide teachers with the knowledge and skills needed to follow the policy. Finally, it is recommended that the schools take the necessary steps to improve the knowledge of secondary school teachers about NEP 2020 to improve student learning and the overall educational process.

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